

Erythrocytapheresis Service in the Basrah: Safety and Efficacy Statistics

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Abstract

One of the methods of treatment of sickle cell anemia is erythrocytapheresis. This disease is widespread throughout the world, including the Middle East. This study has two goals: describe the erythrocytapheresis service at the Center in Basra (Iraq) taking into account the characteristics of the patients and the type of procedure, as well as show the safety profile of erythrocytapheresis using adverse reaction statistics.

Introduction

Background

A single mutation within the β -globin gene causes sickle cell disease (SCD), which includes homozygous mutations (S/S) and combined hemoglobinopathies like heterozygous β^0 -thalassemia (S/ β^0) or another mutation (like HbSC), which may present clinically similarly. When deoxygenated, it causes aberrant hemoglobin polymers to form [1,2] can serve as the etiology for a variety of symptoms and consequences. They stand in for the symptoms of the illness, which include avascular necrosis, sequestration crises, severe chest syndrome, sickle cell retinal damage, and vaso-occlusive crises [3]. The number of people with sickle cell disease grew globally by 41.4% (38.3–44.9) between 2000 and 2021, at 5.46 million (4.62–6.45) to 7.74 million (6.51–9.2) [4].

The process of replacing aberrant red blood cells in a patient's blood with healthy donor red blood cells—either manually or with the aid of an automated cell separator—is known as red cell exchange, or RCE. While the removal of sickle cells is the most common application for this operation for individuals with sickle

cell, it can also help lower the disease load in severe instances of malaria, babesiosis, and some overdose or poisoning situations. RCE helps lower iron overload brought on by top-up transfusion in patients with thalassemia major [5,6]. When used early in the ABO group mismatch transfusions, RCE can save lives. By eliminating HBSS and HBS β cells, RCE in SCD reduces the risk of future vaso-occlusive episodes and increases oxygen capacity for carrying without raising blood viscosity. For people who have homozygous sickle cell disease (SCD), RCE can also be used as a long-term treatment for maintaining low levels of HbS in both initial and secondary stroke prevention [7]. Apheresis is a technique used in automated red blood cell exchange that isolates red blood cells from other components of blood. The RBCs are extracted one by one and replaced with colloid/crystalloid solutions or donor RBCs alone [8,9]. The primary issues with RBC conversion are its expensive nature, as well as the need for specialist personnel and equipment. Sufficient vascular access may be a problem, particularly in people who have had long-term exchanges and small children. While peripheral venous access may be used for most

More Information

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Keywords:

Erythrocytapheresis, automated blood exchange, sickle cell disease

Abbreviations

BCHBD (Basra Center for Hereditary Blood Diseases),
ExBT (exchange blood transfusion),
RCE (red cell exchange)

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treatments, certain individuals may need an arterio-venous fistula or a permanent essential venous catheter [10,11].

Since sickle cell disease is a global condition, many institutions have used erythrocyte apheresis as an option for treatment. In Italy, for instance, the literature supports the utilization of erythrocyteapheresis as a safe and feasible procedure during pregnancy, so long that specific devices and a qualified apheresis team are available [12] and in Belgium, where research indicated that erythrocytapheresis is a potential treatment for iron excess brought on by transfusions [13].

In addition to erythrocytapheresis, sickle cell diseases are extremely common in the Middle East. An example of this can be found in Saudi Arabia, where the University of King Saud Medical City in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia, conducted an observational retrospective study as a review of chronic RBCX in adult individuals with SCD from 2015 to 2019 [14] and in Oman, where research validates future reimbursement concerns and supports the implementation of erythrocytapheresis when compared to alternative transfusion possibilities. Cost reductions from erythrocytapheresis might result in increased adoption. We advise researchers to recalculate these results using the model for each institution separately [15].

In Iraq, erythrocytapheresis also was practiced in many cities where SCD is prevalent like in AL Najaf in Alhassan AL Mujtaba center, Karbala Governorate.

As of right now, there are no published data on the effectiveness and safety of erythrocytapheresis in sickle cell disease.

Historical Background

Basrah Centre for Hereditary Blood Diseases is one of the biggest hematology centers in Iraq on the national base, Basrah governorate contains the largest SCD cohort of the SCD category, to date, more than 5954 patients are registered

Although it was founded in 1998, the apheresis unit was first issued in 2015. first 11 patients were engaged in a prophylactic erythropoiesis, all of them were above the age of 12. The Spectrum Optia® The technique of a Systems of Terumo-BCT Pvt Ltd was utilized in this single apheresis unit, During the Covid-19 period, the unit stopped working due to the loan of the machine to the therapeutic plasma units in the Corona Treatment Centre and due to other technical problems, to resume its work later in 2021 with the faculty of one hematology doctor beside two professional nurses with the introduction of two parallel working machines with a significant expansion in the level of the unit's work in terms of quantity and quality, so that the number of patients benefiting from the service reached more than 45 patients in 2022, then 70 in 2023 and 79 in 2024 from the sickle cell anemia category alone, and other

services were added like leukapheresis and plasmapheresis, A vascular asses of peripheral veins were accessed by a most senior professional nurse CV line is seldom practiced.

The current study is the 1st published descriptive audit to highlight these services.

Aim of the Study

- 1) To elaborate on the erythrocytapheresis service in the Basrah Centre in a descriptive way in regard to patient characteristics and type of the procedure.
- 2) To show the safety profile for the erythrocytapheresis by the adverse reaction statistics.

Methodology

A retrospective, patient records-wise study was conducted for the period from August 2022 to May 2024, data were obtained from the center database, patient records and the electronic database of the erythrocytapheresis unite in the center, data were verified, collected, tabulated, and graphed via Microsoft excel software 2019®.

Procedure: almost the erythrocytapheresis sessions follow the next regulations:

- 1) Vascular asses of peripheral veins were accessed by a most senior professional nurse except one too-young patient
 - 2) The machine settings are set by the blood specialist and unit supervisor, so that the required amount of blood, the duration of the session, and the required PCV and HbS levels are calculated.
 - 3) The pre-procedural assessment included CBC indecent, HbS estimation basic biochemistry including S.Ca.
 - 4) Observation of the patient's vitals and general condition during the procedure
 - 5) Post-procedural Hb S estimation to evaluate the response and effectiveness of the session
- During the sessions, pre-storage leuko-filtered packaged red blood cell preparations (SAGM) that have not been older than one week were employed. High-performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) revealed that all transfused red cell units were heterozygous (positive for sickle cells), and all donors had no family history of illness. The supervising physician determined the quantity and number of red blood cells to be transfused based on the patient's blood volume, goal hemoglobin %, sickling cell percentage, and hemoglobin percentage, among other factors.

Population

All the erythrocytapheresis procedures conducted during the period of the study.

Statistics

Microsoft Excel software 2019® for tabulation percentages and graphing SPSS 2023 for correlational and probability calculations.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Erythrocytapheresis Work in Basrah

Variables	NO.	%	P value
age categories			
< 18			
1 year-6 years	6	7.59%	
7years-12years	37	46.84%	
13 years - 18	29	36.71%	
>18	7	8.86%	
Minimum age	4		
Maximum age	41		
sex			
male	52	65.82%	
females	27	34.18%	
blood group			
A+	17	21.52%	
o+	30	37.97%	
B+	23	29.11%	
AB+	4	5.06%	
A-	1	1.27%	
B-	1	1.27%	
AB-	1	1.27%	
O-	2	2.53%	
Diagnosis			
Sickle cell anemia	58	73.42%	
S/ β thalassemia	20	25.32%	
S/D diseases	1	1.27%	
session statistics			
No. of sessions done	378		
average sessions	4.77		
average period between sessions	63.3		
reduction in Hb S			
average pre S	67.1		
average post apheresis	24.4		
average reduction in Hb S	42.7		
BMI	17.45		
Body wt. Min.	11.97		
Body wt. Max.	42.45		
Average body wight /kg	36.5		

Figure 1: Types of Scd

Figure 2: Age Distribution

Figure 3: Blood Groups Distribution

A total of 378 erythrocytapheresis sessions for a total of 79 patients had been done in the Basra Center apheresis unit for SCD patients, with an average number of sessions for each patient was 4.7 (minimum was 1, max was 22), with an average period between two sessions for all patients of 63.3 days (minimum was 50 max was 222 days), male 65.82%, females 34.18% with a male: female ratio of 1.9. A marked

predominancy of age groups (7 years-12 years) and (13 years –18) (46.84%,36.71%) successively, sickle cell anemia 73.42% was the most category involved, and three blood groups of A+ 21.52%, o+ 37.97%, B+ 29.11% were dominant, BMI statistics was Average BMI was 17.45 body wt. Min. vs. max (11.97kg),(42.45) respectively Average body weight/kg was 36.5 kg.

Table 2: Hb S Reduction Toward Certain Characteristics

	variables	post apheresis Hb S >30%	%	post apheresis Hb S <30%	%
age categories	< 18				
	1 year-6 years	0	0.0%	7	9.9%
	7 years -12 years	6	75.0%	31	43.7%
	13 years - 18	1	12.5%	28	39.4%
	>18	1	12.5%	5	7.0%
sex	male	5	62.5%	47	66.2%
	females	3	37.5%	24	33.8%
blood group	A+	4	50.0%	13	18.3%
	o+	0	0.0%	29	40.8%
	B+	1	12.5%	22	31.0%
	AB+	2	25.0%	3	4.2%
	A-	1	12.5%	0	0.0%
	B-	0	0.0%	1	1.4%
	AB-	0	0.0%	1	1.4%
	O-	0	0.0%	2	2.8%
diagnosis	sickle cell anemia	8	100.0%	50	70.4%
	S/β thalassemia	0	0.0%	20	28.2%
	S/D diseases	0	0.0%	1	1.4%

Average pre-ECP Hb S was 67.1 for all the patients involved average post-ECP was 24.4 with an average reduction in Hb S 42.7, the categories that showed the

more reduction were age groups of 7 years -12 years, and 13 years – 18 (43.7%,39.4%), male sex 66.2%, blood group o+ 40.8%, B+ 31.0%. and in patients with a diagnosis of sickle cell anemia (70.4%).

Table 3: Effect of Certain Variables on ECP Requirements

	variable	average NO. of sessions	average period between sessions	P value
sex	female	4.04	59.6	
	male	5.84	73.07	
age	< 18	5.06	69.26	
	>18	5.17	116.75	
diagnosis	SCA	4.86	62.15	
	S/β	6.25	86.1	

Figure 4: Effect of Certain Variables on ECP Requirements

Males required slightly higher NO. of sessions with females and the period between sessions was higher (59.6,73.07) respectively, age did not seem to be affecting the No. Of sessions when comparing adults below 18 age the period between sessions was greatly higher for adults (69.26,116.75) day respectively,c diseases required more sessions with a higher than SCA (62.15,86.1).

Most of the patients enrolled were subjected to ECP for having interactable unremitting pain(46.84%), sickle CNS disease (20.25%), and bone infarction(7.59%) And for a lesser extent sickle cell hepatopathy at 6.33%, preoperative preparation at 6.33% avascular necrosis (2.53%), and repeated acute chest syndrome (5.06%). Only one patient with multiorgan failure syndrome was subjected to rescue apheresis Other one adult was aiming to support conception for which hydroxyurea was obligatorily interrupted.

Table 4: Case Distribution According to Indications for ECP

indication	No.	%
interactable non remitting pain	37	46.84%
sickle cell hepatopathy	5	6.33%
sickle CNS disease	16	20.25%
preoperative preparation	5	6.33%
avascular necrosis	2	2.53%
bone infarction	6	7.59%
repeated acute chest syndrome	4	5.06%
multiple sickle morbidity	2	2.53%
multiorgan failure syndrome	1	1.27%
preconception via IVF ,need to stop hydroxyurea	1	1.27%
total	79	100.00%

Table 5: Reaction and Complication Observed

complication	NO.	%
alloimmunization	2	20%
acute allergic reaction	3	30%
early febrile reaction	2	20%
hypotension & vomiting	2	20%
hypotension and collapse	1	10%
total	10	12.66%

A total of 10 cases (12.65 %) adverse event was observed regardless the frequency of occurrence ,the

most common was the acute allergic reaction (30%) while alloimmunization acute allergic reaction, early febrile reaction, hypotension & vomiting all occurred in an equal frequency of (20%), and collapse occurred in a single case.

Figure 5: Reaction and Complication

Discussion

Basrah Centre for Hereditary Blood Diseases is one of the biggest hematology centers in Iraq, more than 5954 patients are registered with SCD to date apheresis unite has been issued since 2015.

In this study, the patient characteristics involved 378 erythrocytapheresis sessions for a total of 79 patients that were done in the Basra Center apheresis unit for SCD patients, with an average number of sessions for each patient was 4.7(minimum was 1, max was 22), with an average period between two sessions for all patients of 63.3 days (minimum was 50 max was 222 days), male 65.82%, females 34.18% with a male:female ratio of 1.9.

Numerous television shows have explored single-center experiences with smaller cohorts, such as those in Indonesia where leukocytapheresis, therapy exchange of plasma (TPE), and erythrocytapheresis are currently conducted as part of therapeutic apheresis procedures. Among 137 patients, 204 underwent apheresis treatments between 2009 and 2013 [16], The final percentage of red cell residual values, which were maintained at ≤30%, was attained in all instances in the Indian series, where a total of eighteen patients were evaluated for pre-arthroplasty efficacy [17].

A marked predominancy of age group (7years-12years) and (13 years –18) (46.84%,36.71%) successively, sickle cell anemia 73.42% was the most category involved, which both corresponded to the demographic

characteristics of the center population in general average pre-ECP Hb S was 67.1 for all the patient's involved average post-ECP was 24.4 with an average reduction in Hb S 42.7, the categories that showed the more reduction were age groups of 7 years -12 years and 13 years – 18 (43.7%,39.4%), male sex 66.2%, blood group o+ 40.8%, B+ 31.0%. In patients with a diagnosis of sickle cell anemia (70.4%), so ECP is to be considered almost an effective procedure in the study sample in achieving the target HBS recommended for most of the sickle cell prophylaxis(post-ECP Hb S <30%) a thing which had been supported by many studies like in India [17], in UK [18], and the USA [4], also was greatly supported by the ASH transfusion Guidelines [19] and in certain middle east countries like in Sadi Arabia [14], Oman[15] Lebanon [20] the best peripheral access methods (such as ultrasonography guiding) and access to central venous devices, as well as methods for preserving patency and sterility, were determined by the ASH panel to be the top research priority [19].

Automated RCE increased the odds of achieving the desired preprocedural HbS suppression (odds ratio [OR], 5.5; 95% CI, 1.07-28.22 [21-23] with shorter procedure duration (average of 91 and 115 minutes vs 150 and 257 minutes) [22-24] and increased intervals between procedures (average of 30 and 47 days vs 28 and 35 days) [25].

Similar cohort conducted in Egypt Twenty-one participants were enrolled between December 18, 2017, and December 17, 2022; seventeen (80.9%) were Egyptian, and four (19.1%) were not (three were from Sudan, and one was from Nigeria). A total of 133 sessions, with varying monthly frequencies, had been conducted, mostly during working hours. Every session used central venous access and maintained an isovolumic state. Most of the sessions (n = 78, 58.7%) were able to reach the goal FCR, with the mean final FCR% fraction of 51 having been established from the beginning [26].

Eight patients with sickle cell disease with an average age of 12.1 years who were at high risk of having a first or subsequent stroke had their erythrocytapheresis outcomes examined by Vishinsky et al. series. They were kept at the typical 30% hemoglobin S levels (Hb S) pre-transfusion level.

The safety profile for the experience in this study had been elaborated in the form of the adverse event registered meanwhile which showed that A total of 10 cases (12.65 %) of adverse events was observed regardless of the frequency of occurrence, the most common was the acute allergic reaction (30%) while alloimmunization acute allergic reaction, early febrile reaction, hypotension & vomiting all occurred in an equal frequency of (20%), collapse occurred in single case.

In line with this, several research with comparable safety profiles had been released, In the Egyptian series, most sessions go well with no adverse events (n = 81, 60.9%), with the exception of a few difficulties like not having enough blood (n = 38), low blood pressure (n = 2), and hypocalcemia (n = 2). In contrast, no patient in the Vishinsky et al series experienced complications from the procedure or from using more blood than usual [26,27]. Automated red cell extraction was linked to a higher need for red blood units as compared to simple transfusion [19], nonetheless, it was unrelated to elevated alloimmunization or unfavorable transfusion responses [28,29], The probabilities of getting new alloimmunization for individuals undergoing automated vs manual RCE were shown to be higher in the only trial that examined the two methods (OR, 2.5; 95% CI, 0.07-58.66) [23,27].

Most of the patients enrolled were subjected to ECP for having intractable unremitting pain(46.84%), sickle CNS disease (20.25%), bone infarction(7.59%), And for a lesser extent sickle cell hepatopathy in 6.33%, preoperative preparation 6.33% avascular necrosis (2.53%) and repeated acute chest syndrome (5.06%), preoperative exchange transfusion had been practiced and studies for safety in other series, A prospective one-year study was conducted on 114 SCD patients who were having elective surgery at 31 hospitals in England [30], RCE has been recommended in the majority of trials for SCD and acute chest syndrome [31].

Demetris et al. conducted intriguing research with 88 patients in the UK, yielding inconsistent findings and patient demographics. Of these, 46 patients were female and 42 were males, with ages ranging from 18 to 68 (median age 37). Of the patients, 69 (78%) had Hb SS/Sβ0, 17 (19%) had Hb SC, 2 (2%) had Hb Sβ+, and 1 (1%) had Hb SD Punjab. Of these, 59% were receiving frequent automated red cell exchange and had a history of severe crises that they had experienced repeatedly, also seemed to be helpful for individuals with severe, drug-resistant stuttering priapism and recurring leg ulcers, but patients with pulmonary arterial hypertension had a marked improvement in both their echocardiographic parameters and symptoms. Variations in hemoglobin S a decrease from 44 (17–98) to 12 (2–63) % and an adverse event panel with a lower frequency of alloimmunization (0.027/100 units of red blood cells) and a brief 61% decrease in platelet count (from 357 (74–1037) to 140 (41–575)) were noted following the procedure. These variations were explained by the various genotypic categorizations and complications. There were no hemorrhagic problems linked to this.

Conclusions

Erythrocytapheresis in Basrah is most effective with the use of peripheral vein access and is generally safe with accepted correctable adverse events.

The erythrocytapheresis was mostly effective in age groups of 7 years -12 years and 13 years – 18, male sex, blood group o+ 40.8%, B+, especially in those who have been diagnosed with sickle cell anemia.

Recommendations

Further studies are to be conducted concentrating on the effect of IOL, and sickling-related marker.

A comparable and correlational study design in regarding certain parameters like the type of the procedure, adult vs pediatric experience.

Limitations

Descriptive noncorrelational study design.

An average sample size, not a large one.

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Declaration of interest

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